

	Ellipse	Bowes	Brown Fireside
Thursday, March 25			
Session 1 8-9:30am	<i>Recovery of Sight for the Blind: Panel</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Naomi Haynes • Brian Howell • Joel Robbins 	<i>The Prophetic Imagination in Time & Space</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sam Powell • Orlando Serrano • Paul Jensen 	<i>Brueggemann and His Legacy</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brad Kelle • Jeff Bassett • Colleen Windham/Molly Vetter
Session 2 1:30-3pm	<i>Women's Studies Panel</i>	<i>Art, Justice, and the Imagination I: Art as Prophetic</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brandon Sipes • Dee Dee Richer • Warren Koch 	<i>Disrupting Empire</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joseph Volk • Jacquelyn Winston • Brent Peterson/Stephen Shaw • Eric Lee
Session 3 3:30-5pm	<i>God's Economy I</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Randy Ataide • Paul Tartre • Darel Grothaus 	<i>The Prophetic Imagination Embodied I: The Church in the World</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robert Buck • Karen Crozier • Jin Kim • Jeff Carr 	<i>Prophets of our Time I</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paul Kaak • Terri Marcos • Andrew Hendrixson
Friday, March 26			
Session 4 8-9:30am	<i>Justice and Peace Kiss: Reconsidering Martyrdom & Apocalypse at the Cross</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nathan Kerr • Craig Keene • Mark Bilby 	<i>Prophets of our Time II</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Karl Martin • Diana Cordileone • Thomas Reifer/Christine Holloway 	<i>Art, Justice & the Imagination II: The Artist as Prophet</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Melanie Weaver • Greg Halvorsen Shreck • Tanya Susoev
Session 5 1:30-3pm	<i>'The Myth of Religious Violence' Panel</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • William Cavanaugh • Nathan Kerr 	<i>The Prophetic Imagination Embodied II: Liturgy, Worship & Praxis</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rebecca Laird • George Johnson • Ben Kautzer 	<i>Jesus as Prophet in the Synoptic Gospels</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Michael Lodahl • Jack Hamlin • Gabi-Makusse-Overduin • Tom Phillips
Session 6 3:30-5pm	<i>Art, Justice & the Imagination III: The Art of Prophets</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • John August Swanson • Art Cribbs 	<i>Good News to the Poor: Worker Justice Panel</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laurie Coskey • Taha Hassane • TBA 	<i>God's Economy II: The Year of the Lord's Favor</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wendy Wellman/Stephen Bauman • Mark Russell • Senyo Abjibolosoo
Saturday, March 27			
Session 7 8-9:30am	<i>God's Economy III: Jubilee Economics Panel</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lee van Hamm • Gloria and Ross Kinsler • Dan Swanson • Scott Klinger 	<i>All Creation Groans: Empire & Ecology</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chris Elisara • Maria Pascuzzi • Samy Swayd 	<i>Art, Justice & Imagination IV: Panel</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eric Severson • Karen Marshall • Stacey Barker